

Antecedents to Brand Equity for the Service Industry: A Thematic Analysis

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Abstract

Purpose-Given the increasing contribution of the service industry to the economy, and the dearth of suitable models for measuring the brand equity of services, this research paper aims to bring out the antecedents to brand equity with reference to the service industry

Design/Methodology/Approach- The paper is based on content analysis of research articles from scientific databases, using a qualitative data analysis software NVivo. For a comprehensive understanding of the analysed data, the authors have presented a word cloud and a concept map in the research paper

Findings-The analysis brings out newer antecedents to brand equity like People, Physical evidence, Process and Customer Satisfaction, for the service industry, in addition to those already enunciated in the literature in existing Brand Equity Models

Practical Implications – The outcomes of this paper throw light on the need to expand the existing literature to include the newer antecedents to brand equity with reference to the service industry. Organizations that are a part of the service industry would benefit by focusing on the new antecedents to increase their brand equity and sustain in the competitive market place.

Originality/Value – This research paper contributes to the existing body of literature by bringing out new antecedents to the Brand Equity for Services in addition to the ones that are already listed in the existing literature

Keywords - Brand Equity, Service Industry, Branding Strategy, Thematic Analysis, Antecedents,

Paper Type – Research paper

1. Introduction The relationship between consumers and brands was initially described as "brand equity" in marketing literature.(Wood, 2000) Brand equity produces a certain type of added value for products that supports firms' long-term objectives and potential. Over the past 20 years, brand equity has been thoroughly examined from many angles. It is now commonly acknowledged as a vital success factor for setting businesses and service providers apart from their competitors (Chang et al., 2008). The majority of the literature, meanwhile, focuses on product brand equity. The authors have identified the necessity of reviewing the current brand equity models in light of the service industry in this context

1.1. Need for adapting the existing brand equity models to suit the service industry – Services, by nature are different from physical goods or products. Their inherent characteristics like intangibility, inconsistency, perishability and inseparability pose problems in marketing of the services. Against this backdrop, it is necessary to look at the sufficiency of existing Brand equity Models to suit the Service Industry. (M. M. Sarker et al., 2019) opine that contemporary brand equity models have been recognised and put to the test in the context of service branding, but they are not entirely applicable to the aviation industry. These models are more suited for companies that are primarily focused on products since they downplay the importance of direct service interactions and brand consistency in building airline brand equity. Our discussion and analysis show that while an adaptable service branding model is clearly needed, modern CBBE models are not fully adequate for branding services. Similarly, in the context of the electronic banking industry, (Sanayei, Shaemi, et al., 2013) have added three antecedents as brand image, brand loyalty and perceived quality enriching the existing Consumer Based Brand Equity (CBBE) model.(Guha Roy et al., 2018) have added infrastructure and culture as important antecedents to brand equity with reference to the medical tourism industry. In agreement with the need for adapting the existing brand equity models to suit the service industry, (Uford & Duh, 2021) mention that there have been few research studies on service brands in the examinations into the roots of CBBE.(Skaalsvik & Olsen, 2014) also reiterate that while research on consumer brands appears to be comprehensive and rich, it is less developed and more fragmented when it comes to service brands.

1.2. Existing Models of Brand Equity - In this section, the authors examine the existing Brand Equity Models. There are several models for measuring Brand equity. Most of these models measure the antecedents or the parameters which constitute Brand equity. Popular amongst the models is David Aaker's Brand equity measurement Model. According to Aaker's Model, the five parameters that make up Brand Equity of a Product are Brand Loyalty, Brand Awareness, Perceived Quality, Brand Associations and other Proprietary Assets (Aaker, David A. (1991). *Managing brand equity*. New York: Free Press),(Farjam & Hongyi, 2015). Another Model that is often referred to by Researchers and academicians

is Kevin Lane Keller's Customer Based Brand Equity Model (CBBE model). The building blocks of the CBBE model include Brand Identity (Awareness), Brand Meaning (Performance), Brand Judgements (Perceived Quality), Brand Feelings (Association) and finally Brand Relationship (Brand Loyalty). (Farjam & Hongyi, 2015). Some other models viz. Yoo and Donthu's model 2002, prescribes elements of marketing mix, brand equity dimensions like perceived quality, awareness and brand loyalty as the antecedents to Brand Equity (Yoo & Donthu, 2002), (Farjam & Hongyi, 2015). Similarly we find that Wang and Finn's Model 2013, propagates brand loyalty, brand associations, perceived quality, uniqueness, and emotions of the customer as the major parameters that lead to building brand equity (Wang & Finn, 2013), (Farjam & Hongyi, 2015). However, as mentioned earlier, these models are not sufficient towards the measurement of brand equity for services.

- 2. Method Thematic Analysis of Research papers:** Against this backdrop, the authors adopted a thematic analysis approach of relevant literature available from SCOPUS, Web of Science and Science Direct. The initial search yielded 98 articles from the above-mentioned databases. Some articles were rejected during the review process at the title level, while others were rejected at the abstract level. 48 research papers' full texts were reviewed, and the key themes that emerged were in line with the goal of the study. Care was also taken to ensure that research papers reviewed, covered a variety of industries in the service sector like aviation, banking, tourism, hotel industry and medical tourism to name a few.

A useful method for comparing and contrasting the opinions of numerous research participants and generating unexpected results is thematic analysis. Thematic analysis forces the researcher to manage the data in an organised manner, producing a report that is arranged and understandable, which is useful for summarising significant features of a large data set. (Nowell et al., 2017) (Braun & Clarke, 2008). As a result, the authors find thematic analysis a good fit for this study.

The research papers were imported using NVIVO software version 12.2 from QSR International in Melbourne, Australia. The principal topics and sub-themes were then explored using NVivo, leading to the creation of a project map for understanding the antecedents of Brand Equity in the Service sector. The findings of our thematic analysis are shown in the section that follows.

3. Findings

3.1 Mind Map – A mind map gives a representation of the connections in the data. The NVIVO software was used for creating the mind map with the help of a priori coding based on the antecedents to Brand Equity available in existing Brand Equity models. The mind map shown in Figure 1 highlights the main antecedents to Brand Equity.

Figure 1 – Mind Map of antecedents to Brand Equity for the Service sector

3.2 Discussion on emergent themes: The thematic analysis resulted in two types of themes. One set of themes were the ones that were present in the existing models. The analysis however, also resulted in emergence of new themes which are not present in the existing Brand equity models.

3.2.1 Existing Themes – As mentioned in the Brand Equity Models by Aaker, Keller and other researchers, Brand Awareness, Brand Loyalty, Brand Associations, Perceived Quality and Brand Image have emerged as antecedents to Brand Equity for the Service sector through the analysis. The Authors have presented the same below:

- a. **Brand Awareness:** One of the main pre-cursors to purchasing a brand (and thereby enhancing its equity) is knowing and being aware of the brand. A consumer who does not have the brand in his choice set will not purchase it ever. Given this argument, Brand Awareness is an important antecedent to Brand Equity. In the context of medical tourism (Das & Mukherjee, 2016) (Guha Roy et al., 2018) corroborate this. Similarly (Liu et al., 2017a) also find this relevant with respect to Luxury Hotel branding. Results of the study by (Sürücü et al., 2019) reveal the importance of Brand Awareness as an antecedent to Brand Equity for the Hotel Industry. With respect to the medical services, (Altaf et al., 2018) have found brand awareness to be one of the important antecedents. (Ray et al., 2021) find the same to be true in case of e-Learning platforms. Researchers (Berry, 2000) have also found that in case of service industry, Brand awareness and brand meaning both contribute to brand equity for experienced customers. (Sanayei, Naami, et al., 2013) corroborate this for the education industry. In case of logistics services, (Davis et al., 2009) find Brand awareness to be a reliable antecedent to Brand equity. (Tran et al., 2021a) (Al-Dmour et al., 2013) state that Brand Awareness is a major component of Brand Equity in case of Mobile Apps and Mobile Telecommunication Service. Further (Preko et al., 2022) have found Brand Awareness to have positive and significant impact on Destination Brand Equity. (Shalan et al., 2022) opine that Brand Awareness is an essential antecedent to Brand Equity in case of Banking Industry.

b. Brand Loyalty: Brand Equity of a brand is enhanced only when the Consumer is Loyal to the brand and not only purchases the brand repeatedly but also actively advocates the Brand. As such, Brand Loyalty is an important antecedent for Brand equity. The thematic analysis has revealed that in case of services also, Brand Loyalty acts as a forerunner to Brand Equity. (Das & Mukherjee, 2016) and (Guha Roy et al., 2018) mention that, Brand Loyalty is a major component of Brand equity for the Medical Tourism Services. (Liu et al., 2017a) also find Brand Loyalty relevant in case of Luxury Hotel Services. (Sanayei, Shaemi, et al., 2013) and (Uford & Duh, 2021) find that brand loyalty has a positive impact on Brand equity in case of Electronic Banking service, educational services and the Banking Industry respectively. The study's findings (Chahal & Bala, 2012) confirm that brand loyalty has a significant impact on service brand equity in the healthcare sector.(Tran et al., 2021a) (Fong & Goh, 2021)find Brand Loyalty to be significant to the Brand Equity in case of Mobile apps and the same is found to be true in case of Hotel Industry (Kayaman & Arasli, 2007). Research (Rajab Nikhashemi et al., 2013) has also found that in case of Internet Services as also in case of Banking industry Brand Loyalty has a positive effect on Brand Equity (Shaalán et al., 2022). According to the thematic analysis, authors have found Brand Loyalty to be an antecedent to Brand Equity

c. Brand Associations: The mental connect that a Consumer makes with the brand is Brand Association. Associations are necessary for consumers to be able to instantly recall the brand and to differentiate it from the competitor's brand. Recall and recognition of the brand goes a long way in enhancing the equity of the brand.

(Sanayei, Shaemi, et al., 2013)find brand association as a key brand building criteria of brand equity in case of electronic banking industry. Brand Association was found to be relevant to Brand Equity in case of medical tourism (Guha Roy et al., 2018)(Guha Roy et al., 2022). In case of educational services, (Sanayei, Naami, et al., 2013)found that brand associations have a significant effect on Brand Equity.(Uford & Duh, 2021)(Shaalán et al., 2022) opine that brand association positively influences the Bank's Brand equity in case of Banking services. Brand Association was also found as a major contributor to Brand equity in case of mobile app services (Tran et al., 2021).Brand Association has emerged as an antecedent to brand equity according to the analysis.

d. Perceived Quality - Another important antecedent to Brand equity is the perceived quality. The services being intangible, the measurement of the quality or the value of the service depends to a very large extent on how the consumer perceives the quality of the service.(Das & Mukherjee, 2016) (Guha Roy et al., 2018)(Shriedeh et al., 2017) have found perceived quality to be an important antecedent of Brand equity in case of medical tourism services. Also in case of luxury hotel branding Perceived Quality is found to be a critical component of Brand Equity (Liu et al., 2017b). (Vukasović, 2022) mention that perceived quality has a positive impact on Brand Equity in case of higher education. This is also

corroborated by (Mourad et al., 2011) who posit that perceived quality as a service attribute drives brand equity. Similarly, in case of services provided by cardiac institutes, (Altaf et al., 2018) found that health care service quality had a strong impact on Brand equity of the service (Fong & Goh, 2021). Another service industry, the trade show industry also found the perceived quality of the service provided to be a driver of brand equity (Geigenmüller & Bettis-Outland, 2012). (Sarker et al., 2019) found the same to be true for the airline industry. (Sanayei, Naami, et al., 2013) (Sanayei, Shaemi, et al., 2013) mentioned that perceived quality is a significant component of brand equity for electronic banking services as well as educational services. In case of High-tech service providers like the network service industry also, (He & Li, 2011) it was found that network service quality had a direct impact on brand equity. (Zameer et al., 2019) reiterate that for service sector organisations, service quality excellence serves as a foundation for brand equity. With regards to the healthcare sector, (Chahal & Bala, 2012) found that service brand equity is largely influenced by perceived quality. Further, (Tran et al., 2021) have found this to be true in case of Mobile application services. Similarly (Preko et al., 2022) found the perceived value to be an important antecedent to brand equity in case of destination brand equity. Evidence of perceived quality impacting the brand equity was also seen in case of hotel industry (Kayaman & Arasli, 2007). For the internet Service providers as well as the Banking Industry, perceived quality was found to drive brand equity. (Rajab Nikhashemi et al., 2013) (Shalan et al., 2022)

- e. **Brand Image** – Brand Equity has a lot to do with how the Customer perceives your brand, the image that the customer carries in his/her mind about your brand. A positive image helps to enhance the equity whereas a negative image results in corroding the equity. Evidence for this is found through the thematic analysis.

Brand equity in the hotel sector, including the luxury hotel sector, is proven to be significantly enhanced by the brand image. (Liu et al., 2017) (Sürücü et al., 2019) (Kayaman & Arasli, 2007). For the higher education services, image-related determinants of brand equity were found to be significant (Mourad et al., 2011). The Customer based brand equity in Electronic Banking Services is found to be impacted by Brand Image (Sanayei, Naami, et al., 2013). The same holds true for logistics services (Davis et al., 2009). Findings of the study (Chang et al., 2008) confirmed that brand image was an antecedents of brand equity with respect to the service industry.

The thematic analysis has underlined Brand Image, Perceived Quality, Brand Associations, Brand Loyalty, and Brand Awareness as the precursors to Services Brand Equity. These themes are already existing in the current brand equity models are Brand Awareness. However, the analysis has also thrown up some more antecedents which are presently not a part of the existing Brand Equity Models.

3.2.2 Newly emerged antecedents to Brand equity for Service Industry – The thematic analysis of the literature brought out four new themes as antecedents to Brand Equity for the service Industry. These newly emerged themes are explained below:

a. People/Employees - Services are delivered by people to people. Needless to say, “people” is an important aspect of services and has been incorporated in the Marketing Mix (7P’s) for services. The review of literature has revealed that the behaviour of the staff or employees, the empathy exhibited by them, their competence are factors that are impacting the Brand equity of the service.

For the higher education industry (Vukasović, 2022) (Mourad et al., 2011) have found Staff to be an important component of brand equity. (Sarker et al., 2019) (M. Sarker et al., 2021) have conveyed the same in terms of the direct experience of the customer with the staff being a driver of brand equity for the airline industry. (Iglesias et al., 2019) state that in case of the banking industry, surprisingly, the majority of service brand experience research downplays the value of personnel or employees. They found that employee empathy impact brand equity. For high tech network services (He & Li, 2011) found that, employees of service businesses should exercise caution against over-committing, because doing so could be perceived by clients as corporate hypocrisy and harm the company' brand equity. (Skaalsvik & Olsen, 2014) posit that Service employees interact with the customers developing the service brand and thereby the equity. For medical services specially in case of hospitals, The hospital management should concentrate on the conduct, assurance, and tangibility of the employees. More so on the quality of communication, time taken in responding to queries, and caring attitude of the staff as these characteristics of staff behaviour contribute to Brand Equity (Chahal & Bala, 2012) (Kumar et al., 2013) (Kam Fung so & King, 2010). The importance of people and the consequent service experience was found to be an important component of brand equity for the medical tourism industry (Shriedeh et al., 2017). The hotel Industry, another service industry, that found people elements to positively influence the brand equity (Hilal, 2019). (van Riel et al., 2005) support the finding that brand equity in case of Industrial products and services is affected by people and they play an important role is enhancing the same. (Vatankhah & Darvishi, 2018) also found the same to be true in case of the airline industry

b. Physical Evidence or Physical Quality (infrastructure) – Another new antecedent that emerged from the thematic analysis was Physical Evidence or Physical Quality of the service. Services being intangible, the physical aspects of the service are instrumental in tangibilizing the service. Similar to people, physical evidence is a part of the extended marketing mix for services.

In case of the hotel industry, (Sürücü et al., 2019) (Kam Fung so & King, 2010) advocated that Hotel management should carefully prepare the hotel's physical aspects, especially those that guests can see, since they can enhance brand equity. With regards to medical tourism industry, it was found that infrastructure was found

to be relevant in the context of Customer based brand equity(Guha Roy et al., 2018) (Guha Roy et al., 2022)(Shriedeh et al., 2017). Similarly (Chahal & Bala, 2012) advocated that physical aspects in case of the health care industry impacted the brand equity making it necessary to pay attention to tangibilising the service offering through quality infrastructure.

c. Service Process or Service Systems - Services by nature are process-oriented. Inconsistency in the service process can be a major factor leading to decline of the brand equity of the service. Service Process also forms a part of the extended marketing mix.

For the trade show industry, (Geigenmüller & Bettis-Outland, 2012) state that Service process is a crucial determinant of the service brand equity. Similarly for the hotel industry, process elements are found to positively influence the brand equity (Hilal, 2019). (El Naggar & Bendary, 2017) found that the service experience as a result of the processes was an important antecedent to Brand equity. Similarly (Broyles et al., 2009)opine that the experiential components adds to the brand's equity. Process as one of the antecedents to brand equity is also supported in case of Industrial products and services(van Riel et al., 2005).In case of the airline industry,(Vatankhah & Darvishi, 2018) find that the people and process are vital to building brand equity.

d. Customer Satisfaction - Another new antecedent to brand equity for services, that has emerged through the thematic review is Customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction is paramount to ensure brand equity.

In case of financial services industry (Rambocas & Arjoon, 2020)found that Customer satisfaction had a significant positive impact on brand equity. Referring to the banking Industry (Iglesias et al., 2019) highlight the crucial role that customer satisfaction plays in establishing brand equity . (Zameer et al., 2019) also attribute enhanced brand equity to customer satisfaction.(Broyles et al., 2009)maintain that customer satisfaction leads to enhancement of Brand equity. Further literature (Algharabat et al., 2020) also suggests that affection and cognitive processing leading to experience influence Brand equity .(Kumar et al., 2018) argue that experience leading to customer satisfaction is a driver for brand equity in case of services.

- 4. Word Cloud** - Based on the analysis performed using the NVivo programme, a Word Cloud was created in order to better visualise the data. The relevant words are shown in a word cloud in Figure 2 based on how frequently they appear in the dataset. These frequencies were calculated using data taken from numerous study articles. The highest frequency is shown by words that are larger. As a result of its frequent use, the phrase "Brand" predominates. It is surrounded by words that bear a greater relation to Brand Equity.

Figure 2 – Word Cloud

5. Conceptual Framework for antecedents to brand equity for the service industry –

Based on the various themes that have emerged through the thematic analysis, the authors propose the following concept map as shown in Figure 3. The map illustrated the antecedents to brand equity for the service industry including the existing as well newly emerged antecedents.

Figure 3 – Concept Map showing the existing and newly emerged antecedents to Brand equity for Service Sector

6. Discussions and implications

The thematic analysis provides an in-depth understanding of the antecedents to Brand equity as applicable to the Service Sector. While the themes that are existing in the current brand equity models are definitely proven as antecedents to brand

equity, the need for a few more antecedents given the nature of the service industry has emerged from the analysis.

Services by nature are intangible, inseparable, perishable and inconsistent. These characteristics of services are the main cause of concern for the service provider, given that these characteristics often end up becoming the problem areas. The research synthesis has uncovered four new antecedents to Brand Equity for the service industry, in addition to the existing ones. These include People (Employees and staff), Physical evidence (Infrastructure), Processes (Systems) and Customer Satisfaction

The Brand equity for services needs to be examined from the perspective of the difference in the nature of the services and products.

People – Services are delivered by people to people. Since human intervention is maximum in case of services, the behaviour of the staff and employees of the service provider, the empathy shown by them and the overall culture of the service organization comes under the limelight. It would stand in good stead for service providers to focus on this antecedent of brand equity to ensure that customers are taken care of and the interaction with the employees and staff leaves a positive impact. Professionalism on part of the employees, competence and empathy would be the main drivers. Investing to train employees to achieve this end will help enhance the brand equity

Physical Evidence - Unlike products, services are not tangible. As a result, the customer always perceives a risk when purchasing a service. In order to enhance the brand equity, it is necessary for service organizations to ensure that they tangibilize the service by way of providing physical evidence. The physical evidence includes the infrastructure, the look and feel of the place where the service is being delivered, and other essentials depending on the service being provided. That is in case of a hotel, the décor, the ambience, the cutlery would tangibilize the service, whereas for a hospital the availability of modern equipment, cleanliness, hygiene would do the same. Paying attention to these aspects will help to increase the brand equity for the service industry.

Service Processes - The service process is another antecedent to brand equity. A process that is consumer friendly, not too complicated and easy to navigate will leave a positive impact on the consumer's mind thereby increasing the brand equity. This is especially true for industries like the banking industry, hospitals, Airlines and education. A systematic review of the fail points and problem areas and an analysis of customer complaints can help better the processes

Customer Satisfaction - In case of services there are no measurable quality benchmarks. So, quality of the service is a perceived quality based on the consumer's understanding of the quality. Hence it is of paramount importance that Customer Satisfaction be achieved. A satisfied customer will not only repurchase, but also actively advocate the service and enhance the equity. A feedback system to

understand the lacunae and overcome those can go a long way in ensuring customer satisfaction and subsequently enhanced brand equity

Services by nature are different from products (Physical goods). Hence, designing services marketing strategies requires a different approach. Although, the basic concept of Brand equity remains the same whether for products or services, given the nature of services, a few new antecedents need to be focussed upon. Based on the thematic analysis and the new emergent themes explained above, the authors propose a new brand equity model for antecedents of brand equity for the service sector.

Proposed Model for Brand Equity for Services based on the thematic analysis of Literature

Figure 4 – Proposed Model for antecedents to Brand Equity for Service Industry

7. **Conclusions** - - Ensuring a high brand equity is a given for any organization, be it a product or a service organization. Enhancing the Brand equity can be achieved by focussing on the antecedents of Brand equity. The existing models of Brand equity though robust, focus more on products rather than on services. The authors through their thematic analysis have uncovered four additional The existing models of Brand equity though robust, focus more on products rather than on services antecedents to Brand Equity specifically for the service industry. They have added to the existing literature on Brand Equity by bringing in four additional antecedents namely People, Physical Evidence, Process and Customer Satisfaction. Service organizations looking to enhance brand equity will find it beneficial to focus on these antecedents in addition to the earlier existing ones.

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ANNEXURE 1

Code Book for Antecedents to Brand Equity for the Service Sector

Codes

Name	Description
Brand Equity	Brand equity is the value of a brand, determined by the consumer's perception of its quality and desirability
Brand Associations	The mental connect that a Consumer makes with the brand is Brand Association. Associations are necessary for consumers to be able to instantly recall the brand and to differentiate it from the competitor's brand. Recall and recognition of the brand goes a long way in enhancing the equity of the brand.
Brand Awareness	Awareness of the brand is a pre-requisite for any consumer to buy the brand. Brand awareness is one of the major components of majority of the present Brand equity Models. Unless the consumer is aware of the brand he/she will not purchase it or even consider it in his/her choice set e.g. Aaker's Model and Keller's Model
Brand Image	The image the consumer carries in his/her mind regarding the brand can lead to increasing or decreasing the equity of the brand. Negative publicity or a controversy could lead to a negative image resulting in erosion of the brand equity. Hence Brand Image is an important antecedent of Brand Equity
Brand Loyalty	Purchasing a service once and not going for repeat purchases, will not enhance the brand equity of a service brand. Brand Loyalty from the consumer to purchase the service repeatedly and also recommend it to others is essential for increasing the brand equity.
Customer Satisfaction	A satisfied customer will result in a repeat customer. Satisfaction of the customer will increase the brand equity by ensuring repeat purchases and the customer becoming a brand ambassador and advocating the brand.
People	People are an important aspect of any service since it is through people that the service is manufactured and delivered. Given this, the service experience

Name	Description
	of the Consumer, the behaviour of the employees offering the service, the empathy of the staff would all result in enhancing/decreasing the equity of the service brand.
Perceived Quality	The service being intangible, the measurement of the quality of value of the service depends to a very large extent on how the consumer perceives the service. A positive perception regarding competence, quality and value received by the consumer will enable the enhancement of brand equity for the service. It is also an important antecedent in case of brand equity of physical products.
Physical Evidence	Service being intangible in nature, the physical quality/physical evidence is instrumental in tangibilizing the service to a great extent. The physical evidence plays a major role in enhancing the equity of the brand
Service Process	Service Industry being a process-oriented industry, having processes that are consumer friendly and leading to consumer delight lead to increasing the brand equity of the service